

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Journal of Communication Disorders

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/jcomdis

Storytelling and retelling in students with hearing loss—A comparison between tasks with special consideration of referential elements

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Narrative skills
 Storytelling
 Retelling
 Students with hearing loss
 School-age
 Receptive vocabulary
 Phonological working memory

ABSTRACT

Purpose: Narratives are a fundamental aspect of human communication and they play a critical role in academic success for school-aged children. This study aims to examine the oral narrative skills of German-speaking students with hearing loss who attend inclusive schools, with a particular focus on comparing their abilities in a storytelling and retelling task. Additionally, the study investigates the use of referential elements and functions, and explores the relationship between spoken narrative skills, receptive vocabulary, and phonological working memory to identify factors associated with oral narrative performance.

Methods: The sample consisted of 25 students with hearing loss ($M = 11;0$ years), who completed a standardized storytelling and retelling task, alongside assessments of receptive vocabulary and phonological working memory. Data were analyzed for both macro- and microstructure, as well as referential elements and functions. Correlational analyses were conducted to examine the relationships between narrative skills, receptive vocabulary, and phonological working memory.

Results: Students performed better on the retelling task compared the storytelling task in both macro- and microstructural elements. In their narratives, students predominantly used indefinite and definite noun phrases for character introductions, pronouns for maintaining references, and definite noun phrases for reintroductions. Receptive vocabulary correlated with comprehension questions in storytelling, but not with other narrative parameters.

Conclusion: Different narrative tasks place distinct linguistic demands on students with hearing loss. Retelling tasks provide a more structured method for assessing narrative skills, while storytelling tasks offer a deeper insight into more complex narrative construction. In addition, receptive vocabulary appears to be relevant for macrostructural skills in the storytelling task.

1. Introduction

Storytelling is a cornerstone of human communication across various cultures and languages. As such, narratives play a crucial role in both everyday communication and social participation (Berman & Slobin, 1994; Neitzel & Penke, 2021; Tulviste et al., 2016). Narrative skills typically emerge in early childhood and continue to develop during the school years. Previous research has

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcomdis.2025.106613>

Received 6 May 2025; Received in revised form 28 November 2025; Accepted 21 December 2025

Available online 22 December 2025

0021-9924/© 2025 The Author(s).

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demonstrated that the ability to produce coherent and cohesive narratives is not only a prerequisite for academic success but also a predictor of broader educational outcomes (e.g., Bishop & Edmundson, 1987; Dickinson & Snow, 1987; McCabe & Rollins, 1994). This is particularly evident in relation to key subskills such as reading comprehension, literacy acquisition (e.g., Griffin et al., 2004; Gutiérrez-Clellen, 2002; Pinto et al., 2015), and mathematical performance (O'Neill et al., 2004).

Children with hearing loss face considerable challenges in acquiring spoken language and communication skills, primarily due to reduced or delayed exposure to auditory linguistic input (McCreery & Walker, 2022; Tomblin et al., 2015). This input is crucial not only for fostering language development but also for supporting academic engagement and success. A key competence required for achieving academic language proficiency and effectively participating in (inclusive) classroom learning is the ability to express complex ideas explicitly through language. As students progress through their education, the demands on academic language proficiency intensify. These demands encompass developing a more sophisticated vocabulary and complex grammatical structures, including passive structures, and discourse conventions, such as the use of cohesion devices (Cummins, 2000). Fictional oral narratives exemplify some of the specific challenges of academic language proficiency, as they require decontextualized language to convey meaning independent of contextual support (Dickinson & Porche, 2011; Gagarina & Bohnacker, 2022; Norbury et al., 2014). For students with hearing loss, these increasing demands combined with reduced access to auditory input make it particularly difficult to meet the linguistic and educational expectations in mainstream settings.

While previous research on language development in children with hearing loss has primarily focused on language skills, such as vocabulary and morphosyntax (e.g., Lund, 2016; Werfel et al., 2021), higher-level language skills, such as narrative skills, have received less attention. Given the crucial role of narrative skills in school-aged students for both language development and academic achievement, the present study aims to explore the oral narrative skills of students with hearing loss enrolled in inclusive schools. Since different narrative tasks (e.g., storytelling vs. retelling) place distinct linguistic demands on students, comparing performance across these tasks provides valuable insights into their language comprehension, processing, and production abilities, while also revealing specific strengths and areas for improvement. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the narrative abilities of this population across these two different narrative tasks.

1.1. Analyzing narratives

Analyzing narrative skills is a reliable and ecologically valid approach for diagnosing language acquisition delays in children (e.g., Cleave et al., 2010; Gagarina et al., 2019a; Govindarajan & Paradis, 2019). The method of data collection plays a critical role in the analysis of narrative skills (Meier & Neitzel, 2023). Duinmeijer and colleagues (2012) classify various elicitation methods, with one key distinction between auditory and visual stimuli. Visual stimuli typically involve storytelling based on a single image, a sequence of pictures, or a (wordless) picture book, whereas auditory stimuli include the presentation of a theme or an entire story for retelling using picture stories/books or films. In the following, we use the term *storytelling* to refer to narratives generated solely from visual stimuli, while narratives produced from both auditory and visual input are classified as *retelling* (see also Meier & Neitzel, 2023). These different types of narratives place distinct cognitive and linguistic demands on the narrator. In storytelling tasks, the provided visual stimuli must be cognitively processed, abstracted into a mental concept, and then verbalized (Becker, 2017). Storytelling is generally considered a more natural and spontaneous form of narration compared to retelling tasks, which are often more structured (Holck et al., 2011). In contrast, retelling tasks typically impose lower cognitive demands, as the content and structure of the story are already linguistically predetermined (Becker, 2017; Boudreau, 2008; Lindgren, 2023).

Narrative skills can be analyzed at two distinct levels: macrostructure and microstructure. Macrostructure refers to the global organization and content structure of a story and is often described using the story grammar framework proposed by Stein and Glenn (1979). The present study draws on the multidimensional theory of narrative organization (see Lindgren et al., 2023), which builds on the story grammar framework by conceptualizing narrative macrostructure as an interplay of qualitative and quantitative dimensions, as well as factual and inferential components, considered across both narrative production and comprehension processes.

The macrostructure encompasses several key elements, including goals (G), attempts (A), outcomes (O), and internal states (IS), which are systematically organized into episodes. From a quantitative perspective, the macrostructure is characterized by the total number of these components, along with the inclusion of the setting. The qualitative dimension reflects the narrative's complexity, which is assessed by examining the interconnections between the core episodic components (i.e., goal, attempt, and outcome) (Lindgren et al., 2023).

Microstructural analyses on the other hand focus on the linguistic organization and construction of a coherent narrative at the lexical, morphological, and syntactic levels (Justice et al., 2006; Govindarajan & Paradis, 2022; Kavar, 2021; Kavar et al., 2019). These analyses are typically assessed using measures such as productivity (total number of words and utterances), lexical diversity (number of different words), and syntactic complexity (mean length of utterances; MLU; Govindarajan & Paradis, 2022; Licandro, 2016).

1.2. Establishing narrative coherence

The construction of a well-formed and coherent narrative is a complex process that necessitates the integration of cognitive skills and advanced linguistic abilities, including lexical and morphosyntactic competences (Norbury et al., 2014; Vandewalle et al., 2012). A significant challenge in storytelling is the detachment of the story's spatial and temporal context from the immediate situation. Consequently, effective storytelling requires structuring the events in a temporally and causally coherent manner, ensuring the listener to follow what happened, to whom, and for what reason (Gagarina & Bohnacker, 2022). To maintain coherence across sentences and

events, various linguistic devices are employed, such as conjunctions (e.g., and, but; Czech, 2020; Pasch, 2004; Pasch et al., 2003) and referential elements like pronouns, which establish connections between sentences (Klages & Gerwien, 2020). According to Bamberg (1987), the selection of referential expressions in narratives is guided by three main functions: introducing a character with new information, maintaining a previously mentioned character, and reintroducing a character whose reference has been reactivated. These processes require the use of linguistically appropriate forms that adhere to the morphosyntactic rules of the language and reflect the information status of the referent (Gagarina & Bohnacker, 2022; Tsimpli et al., 2016). In German, these distinctions are expressed through specific morphological markers, and there are clear discourse-pragmatic rules governing the appropriate use of different forms (e.g., Eisenberg, 2013). Indefinite noun phrases or articles typically introduce new referents unknown to the listener, whereas definite noun phrases or articles refer to known referents, providing the necessary lexical information to establish correct reference (Ariel, 1990; Gundel & Johnson, 2013; Gundel et al., 1993). Pronouns are used to reintroduce or refer to a character when the listener is already familiar with the referent (Lindgren et al., 2022). In fictional narratives, children encounter the challenge of introducing and maintaining characters without shared visual attention, necessitating linguistic explicitness and the use of appropriate forms to indicate the characters' information status. However, children often struggle to adapt their references to the listener's perspective, particularly when multiple references and topic shifts occur (Gagarina & Bohnacker, 2022; Hickmann et al., 2015; Lindgren et al., 2022). This difficulty may be amplified in children with hearing loss, who frequently show delays in Theory of Mind development—a capacity closely tied to perspective-taking in discourse (Huttunen & Ryder, 2012; Peterson & Slaughter, 2006). The acquisition of German (in)definiteness markers typically begins between the ages of two and three years and continues to develop throughout childhood (Clahsen et al., 1994; Eisenbeiss, 2000; Kupisch et al., 2009). Research on narratives in typically developing children suggests that the ability to appropriately introduce characters develops gradually, with some children mastering this skill only between the ages of seven and nine (e.g., Colozzo & Whitely, 2014; Hickmann et al., 1996; Schneider & Hayward, 2010; Serratrice, 2007).

Another factor in maintaining narrative coherence is the use of appropriate vocabulary and morphosyntactic skills (Melzi & Caspe, 2017; Tomasello, 2000; Westby et al., 1989). Lexical proficiency is a vital prerequisite for effective storytelling, as vocabulary knowledge significantly influences the development of macrostructural skills (e.g., Heilman et al., 2010; Jones et al., 2016). These skills enhance narrative organization, particularly in children whose grammatical and syntactic abilities are still developing (Heilman et al., 2010; Norbury & Bishop, 2003; Uccelli & Páez, 2007). Deficits in morphosyntactic skills can hinder the expression of complex relationships within a narrative, as syntactic knowledge – such as the use of cohesive devices – is essential for sustaining narrative coherence (Bishop & Donlan, 2005; Norbury & Bishop, 2003). For instance, the incorrect or ambiguous use, or the omission of referential elements, such as pronouns, can cause confusion, making it difficult for the listener to identify who is performing actions. Furthermore, the ability to integrate linguistic information and actively retrieve sequences of events in narrative production is related to phonological working memory capabilities (Blom & Boerma, 2016; Dodwell & Bavin, 2008).

1.3. Underlying abilities for narrative production in children with hearing loss

The level of a child's language development is a crucial factor influencing both linguistic expression and narrative quality (Khan et al., 2021). Children with hearing loss often face challenges across all domains of spoken language development, including phonological working memory (McCreery & Walker, 2022; Tomblin et al., 2015), with these difficulties potentially persisting into school age (Tomblin et al., 2015). Research indicates that children with hearing loss typically exhibit reduced phonological working memory capabilities compared to their peers without hearing loss (McCreery & Walker, 2022; Tomblin et al., 2015). Phonological working memory encompasses not only the capacity for phonological short-term memory but also other language processing skills in children. This includes auditory and phonological analysis of pseudowords, phoneme differentiation and identification, memorization of phonemes in the correct order, and their accurate reproduction (Ulrich, 2016).

Limitations in phonological working memory capacity can thus impact multiple levels of language acquisition, including phonological, lexical, morphological, and syntactic development (Archibald & Gathercole, 2006; Montgomery & Evans, 2009). Furthermore, studies have demonstrated that children with hearing loss experience significant deficits in vocabulary (Davidson et al., 2019; Hardebeck et al., 2024; Lund, 2016; Walker et al., 2019), as well as in morphology and syntax (Boons et al., 2013; Klieve et al., 2023; Ruigendijk & Friedman, 2017; Schouwenaars et al., 2019; Werfel et al., 2021). The language development of children with hearing loss varies individually and is influenced by factors such as the degree of hearing loss and the age of diagnosis (Cupples et al., 2018).

1.4. Research on narrative skills in children with hearing loss

Research on the narrative skills of children with hearing loss is limited, often focusing on a single narrative task, either storytelling (e.g., using picture stories or videos; Jones et al., 2016; Zanchi et al., 2021) or retelling (where the examiner narrates a story, and the child reproduces it; Boons et al., 2013; Klein & Wie, 2014). The results from both storytelling and retelling contexts show considerable variability, with some studies reporting no differences (for storytelling: e.g., Asker-Árnason et al., 2012; Hardebeck et al., 2024; and Jones et al., 2016, at the macrostructural level; Breland et al., 2022, at the microstructural level; for retelling: Klein & Wie, 2014, at both levels) and others finding significant differences when compared to typically hearing children (for storytelling: Zanchi et al., 2021, for one macrostructural parameter; Asker-Árnason et al., 2012; Hardebeck et al., 2024; and Jones et al., 2016, at the microstructural level; for retelling: Boons et al., 2013, at both levels). A key challenge in comparing these findings is the variation in methodologies employed. For instance, some studies assessed children's narrative skills in both spoken and signed language (e.g., Crosson & Geers, 2001; Huttunen & Ryder, 2012), while others focused solely on spoken language (e.g., Boons et al., 2013; Klein & Wie, 2014; Zanchi et al., 2021). In addition, most of the studies discussed have examined correlations between narrative skills and

other language abilities. For example, Jones and colleagues (2016) found that expressive vocabulary was correlated with both macrostructural and microstructural narrative skills in a storytelling task, while Boons et al. (2013) identified positive correlations at the microstructural level in a retelling task. Klein and Wie (2014) reported that both expressive and receptive language skills were linked to measures of narrative skills. Additionally, Hardebeck and colleagues (2024) explored the relationship between receptive vocabulary, phonological working memory, and narrative skills in a storytelling task. Their findings indicated that stronger phonological working memory was associated with more advanced story structures and greater story complexity at the macrostructural level. In terms of microstructure, higher receptive vocabulary was associated with greater lexical diversity and a lower number of C-units (Hardebeck et al., 2024).

The only study to date that used a storytelling and a retelling in children with hearing loss was conducted by Walker and colleagues (2023). They reported that children with hearing loss exhibited significant deficits in macrostructural skills compared to their typically hearing peers, with these differences being more pronounced in the retelling task than in the storytelling task. The study also explored factors influencing narrative performance in both tasks, identifying vocabulary, phonological working memory, and grammar as key determinants in the relationship between narrative skills in storytelling and hearing status. In contrast, grammar emerged as the primary influencing factor for the retelling tasks. Overall, the storytelling task appeared more challenging than the retelling task for all children, which the authors attributed to the absence of a modeled narration (Duinmeijer et al., 2012; Schneider & Dubé, 2005; Walker et al., 2023). Consequently, both groups achieved higher scores in the retelling task. The authors suggested that narrative retelling may be a more sensitive measure of language difficulties in young children with hearing loss, though the underlying reason remains unclear (Walker et al., 2023). This study did not specifically target microstructural parameters. Notably, no research has directly compared storytelling and retelling in children with hearing loss, limiting our understanding of how these children process and produce language across different contexts. Since storytelling and retelling engage distinct cognitive and linguistic skills, investigating both tasks could provide deeper insights into the development of narrative abilities in students with hearing loss.

Previous research indicates that retelling tasks generally elicit stronger narrative performance than storytelling. In children without developmental language disorders (DLD), retelling leads to more episodically complete stories with more content elements and greater length (Becker, 2017; Lever & Sénéchal, 2011; Meier & Neitzel, 2023; Schneider & Dubé, 2005). Studies on children with DLD similarly report that prompts greater lexical diversity, though not necessarily higher syntactic complexity as measured by MLU (Duinmeijer et al., 2012; Wofford et al., 2022). Findings based on the Multilingual Assessment Instrument for Narratives (MAIN) likewise show that children perform better in retelling with respect to story structure, comprehension, and in some cases MLU (Kunnari et al., 2016; Lindgren, 2023; Otwinowska et al., 2020; Roch et al., 2016; Wehmeier, 2019). Children with or at risk for DLD also tend to achieve higher comprehension scores in retelling (Kuvač Kraljević et al., 2020; Sheng et al., 2020), although some studies report no differences between task types (Kunnari & Välimaa, 2020; Mavis et al., 2016).

Only a few studies have examined the use of referential expressions in narrative discourse among preschool children, focusing on both monolingual and bilingual populations with and without DLD. Lindgren and Vogels (2018) investigated monolingual Swedish preschoolers' use of referential expressions in a storytelling task using MAIN. Their findings indicated that children distinguished between reintroducing and maintaining referents, with definite noun phrases predominantly used for reintroductions and pronouns for reference maintenance.

Lindgren et al. (2022) reported that Swedish-German children shifted from primarily using pronouns at age four to predominantly using indefinite noun phrases by age six, suggesting increasing consistency and appropriateness in referential expression use with age. However, research on the use of referential elements in children with hearing loss remains limited. Klein and Wie (2014) and Boons et al. (2013) found no differences in the use of referential element between children with and without hearing loss in retelling tasks. Klein and Wie (2014) assessed referential elements using the Narrative Scoring Scheme (NSS) by Heilmann et al. (2010), while Boons et al. (2013) analyzed the number of protagonists, character introductions, and the percentage of incorrect introductions. In contrast, Jones et al. (2016) found that children with hearing loss performed significantly worse in a storytelling task, particularly in clarity of character introduction (e.g., using indefinite pronouns) and maintenance (e.g., correct use of pronouns). While these studies assessed referential expression use through the NSS (see Klein & Wie, 2014) or custom scoring schemes (see Boons et al., 2013; Jones et al., 2016), no research has directly examined referential element use and functions across two narrative tasks in children with hearing loss.

1.5. The current study

Given the crucial role of narrative skills in language development and for academic language proficiency, this study investigates the oral narrative skills of students with hearing loss attending inclusive schools. Specifically, it seeks to evaluate the performance in storytelling and retelling tasks, addressing the distinct linguistic demands of each task type and the limited research directly comparing them. In addition to macrostructural aspects, this study also considers microstructural skills. In light of the research gap concerning students with hearing loss, this study focuses specifically on this population and aims to provide insights for the diagnostic and educational assessment of their narrative skills.

To explore potential task-related differences, the following research question is posed:

What are the differences between storytelling and retelling tasks in students with hearing loss at the macro- and microstructural levels?

Based on previous findings with typically developing children and the preliminary findings of Walker et al. (2023) on children with hearing loss, we predict that students with hearing loss will perform better on retelling tasks compared to storytelling tasks, both at the macro- and microstructural levels.

Additionally, existing studies on the oral narrative abilities of children with hearing loss have rarely investigated the use of referential elements. Referential elements are essential for establishing coherence within a narrative, and their realization – i.e., the

choice and timing of referential elements – is language-dependent. To date, no study has examined the use of referential elements and functions in narratives produced by German-speaking students with hearing loss. Therefore, we focused on the following second research question:

What are the differences in the use of referential elements and functions between storytelling and retelling tasks in students with hearing loss?

Since previous studies have not compared the referential elements and their functions across two narrative tasks, establishing clear expectations remains challenging. On the one hand, the structure of the retelling task, including the provided narrator model, may support the use of more referential elements and pragmatically appropriate referential functions in the retelling task compared to the storytelling task. On the other hand, students may use a similar number of referential elements and employ pragmatically appropriate referential functions in both tasks. Further research is needed to explore how lower-level language skills, such as receptive vocabulary and phonological working memory, influence the oral narrative skills of students with hearing loss, particularly across different narrative tasks. Therefore, we aimed to investigate how these language skills affect the performance of students with hearing loss in both storytelling and retelling tasks:

How do receptive vocabulary and phonological working memory relate to narrative skills at the macro- and microstructural levels in storytelling and retelling tasks? Do these relationships differ depending on the narrative task?

We anticipate to find correlations between lower-level language skills and narrative abilities in both tasks, with stronger lower-level language skills facilitating the expression of more advanced narrative skills. We hypothesize that this effect will be more pronounced in the storytelling task compared to the retelling task, due to the greater cognitive and linguistic demands involved in storytelling.

2. Methods

This study was designed as an exploratory, cross-sectional study and is part of a larger mixed-methods project, integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches to examine language development and school participation in students with hearing loss (see Hardebeck et al., 2025).

2.1. Participants

Participants were 27 German-speaking students with hearing loss between the ages of 7;1 and 16;6 ($M = 11;0$ years), including 13 female and 14 male students. Students were eligible for participation if they had a diagnosed uni- or bilateral hearing loss greater than 25 dB, were enrolled in grades 2–10 of mainstream schools, and primarily used spoken German for communication. Two participants were excluded from the study: one for not completing the narrative tasks, and the other since they did strictly speaking not have a hearing loss, but an auditory processing and perception disorder. For this exploratory study, we recruited a diverse group of students with hearing loss to assess the range of their narrative skills across two narrative tasks and to investigate the relationship between these skills, receptive vocabulary, and phonological working memory across various grades and school types. The aim was to gain insights into their language comprehension and production skills. Participants were recruited through their schools and via an advertisement in

Table 1
Participant characteristics and lower-level language skills.

Participant	Gender	Age at testing	Degree of hearing loss	Hearing device(s)	PPVT-4 t-score	Mottier t-score
01	F	8;4	Mild	Bilateral HAs	56	60.4
02	M	13;0	Profound	Bilateral CIs	48	49.5
03	M	7;9	Profound	CI+HA	70	67.5
04	M	16;6	Moderate to severe	Unilateral HA	55	66.5
05	F	8;0	Moderate	Bilateral HAs	44	44.2
06	M	9;0	Moderate to severe	Unilateral HA	43	49.3
07	F	12;2	Severe to profound	Bilateral HAs	37	32.5
09	F	13;6	Profound	Unilateral CI	43	48.0
10	F	13;11	Profound	Bilateral CIs	39	36.0
11	M	11;10	Severe	Bilateral HAs	31	17.0
12	F	9;5	Severe to profound	Unilateral HA	43	36.6
13	F	8;3	Moderate to severe	Bilateral HAs	27	37.7
14	F	7;4	Moderate to severe	Bilateral HAs	43	56.7
15	M	13;9	Mild	Bilateral HAs	46	39.2
16	M	9;4	Moderate to severe	Unilateral HA	55	51.8
17	M	13;10	Profound	Bilateral HAs	51	48.0
18	M	8;9	Moderate to severe	Unilateral HA	56	66.5
19	F	7;1	Profound	Unilateral HA	67	64.8
20	F	9;9	Profound	Bilateral CIs	47	49.3
22	F	15;1	Moderate to severe	Bilateral HAs	46	39.2
23	M	9;11	Moderate to severe	Bilateral HAs	40	54.1
24	M	13;6	Severe	Bilateral HAs	43	48.0
25	M	11;8	Moderate to severe	Bilateral HAs	47	61.8
26	F	9;11	Mild to moderate	Bilateral HAs	46	41.2
27	M	13;2	Moderate to severe	Bilateral HAs	45	57.4

the regional newspaper. According to parental reports (based on questionnaires, see Supplementary Material 1), the children's hearing loss was diagnosed at an average age of 3;1 year, with degrees of hearing loss ranging from mild to profound. Depending on the degree of hearing loss, four children were fitted with cochlear implants (CIs), twenty with hearing aids (HAs), and one with both. Of these, seven students had unilateral hearing loss, and eighteen students had bilateral hearing loss (see Table 1). Initial intervention was typically initiated at an average age of 3;4 years. Seventeen of the students had received speech and language intervention in the past. All students attended inclusive schools and primarily used spoken language for communication. Out of the 25 students, four are simultaneous bilinguals (three speak Kurdish and one speaks French alongside German).

2.2. Materials and general procedure

Ethics approval for data collection was granted by the central ethics committee of the Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg. Students were assessed in a quiet room at their school or in an office at the Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg in a one-on-one setting. The whole procedure lasted around 90 min and the students received a small present to thank them for participating.

For assessing receptive vocabulary, the German version of the Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test (PPVT-4; Lenhard et al., 2015) was used. In this task, students were asked to choose the picture that fits most from four pictures corresponding to a spoken word. Raw scores were converted into age-standardized t-scores based on the normative data provided in the test manual, with a mean of 50 and a standard deviation of 10. This means that a t-score of 60 or higher reflects relatively strong performance for the child's age in receptive vocabulary or phonological working memory, whereas a t-score of 40 or lower indicates relatively weak performance in these areas. These t-scores were used in further analyses to adjust the PPVT-4 scores for age-related effects. The Mottier-Test was used for assessing phonological working memory (Mottier, 1951). Students were asked to immediately repeat pseudowords that were spoken to them. These pseudowords consist of simple consonant-vowel combinations, with the length increasing from two-syllable to six-syllable words. A maximum of 30 points can be reached (Ulrich, 2016). For the Mottier-Test, t-values according to Wild and Fleck (2013) were used for further analyses.

Storytelling and retelling skills were assessed using the standardized Multilingual Assessment Instrument for Narratives (MAIN; Gagarina et al., 2019b). The instrument contains four comparable stories with six pictures each. For our study, we used the "Baby Birds" and "Cat" stories. Every story consists of an introduction of a setting (place and time) and three episodes with a main story structure (goals, attempts and outcomes) and internal state terms representing initiating events and reactions. According to the testing protocol for the storytelling task, students were instructed to carefully look at the pictures and tell their own story without support from the examiner. For the retelling task, the students were also asked to closely examine the pictures. However, the examiner first told the story and then asked the child to retell the story. Both tasks allowed the students to see the pictures during the telling of the story. To assess the students' understanding of the story, students were asked ten questions from the MAIN protocol about the story for both tasks. The narratives and answers of the comprehension questions were recorded with an Olympus linear PCM recorder.

Data collection was conducted by the first author (LH), a doctoral student with a master's degree in special needs education and practical experience in diagnostics. The audio recordings were transcribed by the third author (PB) following the Codes for the Human Analysis of Transcripts (CHAT) conventions of the Child Language Data Exchange System (CHILDES) (MacWhinney, 2000). Unrelated utterances from both the child and the examiner, such as questions about word meanings or remarks about events outside the room, were transcribed but excluded from the analysis. Utterances were segmented into communication units (C-units; Loban, 1976), which are syntactic units that consists of a main clause along with all dependent elements, including subordinate clauses (Retherford, 2000). Repetitions that contributed no additional meaning to the story (e.g., "The bird...the baby bird was scared") and filler words (e.g., "mhm"; "ähm") were excluded from the analysis. In the case of corrections, only the corrected form was assessed. Unintelligible utterances were also excluded from further analysis.

2.3. Coding and measures

The macrostructure was evaluated using the MAIN protocol (see Gagarina et al., 2019b). A total of 17 points were awarded for the story structure. One or two points were assigned for the setting (place and/or time). Five points could be achieved for each of the three episodes: one point could be scored for each event (goal, attempt and outcome) and for two internal state terms. For the structural complexity, the students could receive a maximum of 12 points, with four points possible for each of the three episodes. Further information on the assessment of structural complexity can be found in Hardebeck et al. (2024). In addition, a child received one point for each correctly answered comprehension question, resulting in a total of ten points.

To assess the microstructural parameters, measures of productivity, lexical diversity, and syntactic complexity were used, as these are all sensitive markers of children's language abilities (e.g. Justice et al., 2006; Uccelli & Páez, 2007) and enabled us to compare our data to former studies, such as Zanchi and colleagues (2021) or Jones and colleagues (2016). The calculations were conducted using the Computerized Language Analysis (CLAN; MacWhinney, 2000) software. To measure productivity, the total number of words and the C-units were calculated using the CLAN command *freq*. In order to calculate the lexical diversity, the CLAN word list obtained via the *freq* command was transferred to an Excel worksheet. The number of different words was then determined by lexicographically reducing the inflectional forms of a word to its basic form to avoid inflating the number of different words through grammatical variations (Bedore et al., 2010). The lemmas were manually organized into the respective basic form of a word, whereby grammatical variants were considered (e.g. *have*, *has*, *had* as variants of *have*). As part of the lemmatization, composites were divided into their corresponding word stems. The lexical diversity was then calculated by dividing the lemmas determined by the total number of words. As a measure of syntactic complexity, the MLU, the average length of C-units in words, was computed using the *mlu* command.

We analyzed the referential function of the referential expressions, distinguishing between first introduction, maintenance, and reintroduction of referents (following Lindgren & Vogels, 2018). Referential expressions were coded into four categories: indefinite and definite noun phrases (including possessives like “his ball”), pronouns (i.e. independently used personal, relative, and demonstrative pronouns), and bare nouns (nouns without a determiner) for a selection of the introduced characters. For the storytelling task, the selected characters were “Mother and Baby Birds”, “Cat and Dog”, and the inanimate objects “Worms” and “Food/Feed”. For the retelling task, the selected characters were “Cat”, “Butterfly”, and “Boy”, along with the inanimate objects “Ball”, “Bucket with Fish”, and “Fishing Rod”. MAXQDA (VERBI Software, 2021) was used for the coding process.

First introduction was coded at the initial mention of the argument. Maintenance (1a) was classified when the referent had been mentioned in the preceding clause, while reintroduction (1b) was used if the referent had been introduced but not in the previous clause (Lindgren & Vogels, 2018). The classification of referential function was independent of the grammatical accuracy of the child’s referring expression, including correct gender or case marking.

(1) a. „Die Katze sah den Eimer mit dem Fisch vom Angeln. Sie rannte dahin.“ (KI18)

“The cat saw the bucket with the fish from fishing. She ran towards it.” b. „Der Junge holt mit der Angel den Ball wieder zurück. Die Katze geht zum Eimer und nimmt sich einen Fisch. Der Junge freut sich, dass er seinen Ball wieder hat.“ (KI16)

“The boy fetches the ball back with the fishing rod. The cat walks to the bucket and takes a fish. The boy is happy to have his ball back.”

Reliability

The analysis of the macro- and microstructure of the narratives was conducted by the third author (PB). To determine interrater reliability, twenty percent of the corpus was transcribed and macro- and microstructure analyzed independently by the first author (LH). Both raters received comprehensive training in the procedure to ensure consistent application of the evaluation criteria. Any disagreements were resolved through consensus. Interrater reliability, assessed using the Intraclass Correlation Coefficient, was excellent across all measures, with storytelling ranging between 0.87 and 0.98, and retelling ranging 0.90 and 0.98.

2.4. Data analysis

The research questions were addressed using descriptive and inferential statistical analyses. In order to evaluate the differences between the storytelling and retelling task types for all narrative parameters, *t*-tests were carried out. Effect sizes were interpreted using Cohen’s *d* (Cohen, 1988), assuming a small effect at $d = 0.2$, a medium effect at $d = 0.5$ and a large effect at $d \geq 0.8$. Statistical significance was confirmed at $p < .05$. Spearman rank-order correlations were conducted to examine the relationships between storytelling skills, receptive vocabulary, and phonological working memory, as well as between retelling skills, receptive vocabulary, and phonological working memory. Spearman rank-order correlations were used to account for the relatively small sample size and the heterogeneity of the participant group. Effect sizes were estimated following Cohen’s (1988) criteria, where $r = 0.10$ was considered a small effect, $r = 0.30$ a medium effect, and $r = 0.50$ a large effect.

3. Results

This study explored the oral narrative skills of students with hearing loss across two tasks: storytelling and story retelling. Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics and *t*-test results comparing the macro- and microstructure between the storytelling and retelling task.

Descriptive statistics for receptive vocabulary and phonological working memory show that participants’ receptive vocabulary *t*-scores ranged from 31 to 70 ($M = 47$, $SD = 8.9$), and phonological working memory *t*-scores ranged from 17 to 67.5 ($M = 49$, $SD = 12.4$). These *t*-scores are standardized based on normative data from typically developing children. Overall, the results suggest that, on average, the students scored close to the normative mean. According to the test manuals, *t*-scores between 40 and 60 are considered within the average range, though individual scores varied, with some children performing below and others above the average range (see Table 1).

Regarding the first research question, the descriptive statistics indicate higher mean values for all parameters assessed in the retelling task at both the macro- and microstructural levels. The only exception is lexical diversity, which is higher in the storytelling

Table 2
Macro- and microstructure scores and between-task comparison.

Variable	Storytelling		Retelling		<i>t</i> (24)	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
Story structure	8.72	1.99	10.52	1.90	4.50	<0.001	0.90
Structural complexity	4.28	2.13	5.96	2.05	2.46	.021	0.49
Comprehension questions	7.96	1.74	9.00	1.08	2.83	.009	0.57
TNW	86.52	24.24	114.56	23.21	4.67	<0.001	0.93
TNDW	47.00	10.35	55.76	11.08	3.51	.002	0.70
Lexical diversity	0.554	0.057	0.490	0.041	-4.56	<0.001	-0.91
Number of C-units	9.92	2.72	12.12	2.59	3.54	.002	0.71
Syntactic complexity	9.15	2.30	10.08	2.30	2.29	.031	0.46

Note. *d* = Cohen’s *d*; TNW = total number of words; TNDW = total number of different words.

task. T-tests were performed to statistically assess the differences in all narrative parameters between the storytelling and retelling tasks. At the macrostructural level, significant differences were found in story structure ($t(24) = 4.50, p < .001, d = 0.90$), story complexity ($t(24) = 2.46, p = .021, d = 0.49$), and comprehension questions ($t(24) = 2.83, p = .009, d = 0.57$), with all parameters being higher in the retelling task. Concerning the microstructure, significant differences were observed between the two narrative tasks across all parameters. While the narratives in the storytelling task exhibited greater lexical diversity ($t(24) = -4.56, p < .001, d = -0.91$), those in the retelling task contained a higher total number of words ($t(24) = 4.67, p < .001, d = 0.93$), a greater number of different words ($t(24) = 3.51, p = .002, d = 0.70$), more C-units ($t(24) = 3.54, p = .002, d = 0.71$), and increased syntactic complexity ($t(24) = 2.29, p = .031, d = 0.46$).

In relation to the second research question, the use of referential elements and functions in both the storytelling and retelling tasks was analyzed. The absolute numbers and percentage distribution of referential elements within each functional category are provided (see Tables 3 and 4, and Figs. 1 and 2).

In terms of referential function, a total of 463 referring expressions were analyzed in the storytelling condition, and 637 in the retelling condition. Within the category of first introductions ($n = 132$ in storytelling and $n = 153$ in retelling), noun phrases were the most common in both conditions. Definite noun phrases appeared 58 times in storytelling (43.94 %) and 56 times in retelling (36.60 %). Indefinite noun phrases occurred 54 times in storytelling (40.91 %) and 83 times in retelling (54.25 %). Bare nouns were used less frequently, with 20 instances in storytelling (15.15 %) and 14 in retelling (9.15 %). Notably, pronouns were not used for first introductions. Among the bare nouns, only two instances in storytelling and five in retelling task were grammatically incorrect. The remaining bare nouns referred to plural forms.

In the maintenance category ($n = 144$ in storytelling and $n = 193$ in retelling), pronouns were most frequently used, occurring 72 times in storytelling (50.00 %) and 144 in retelling (74.61 %). Definite noun phrases followed, appearing 69 times in storytelling (47.92 %) and 45 times in retelling (23.32 %). Indefinite noun phrases played a minor role, appearing twice in storytelling (1.39 %) and three times in retelling (1.55 %). Bare nouns were used only once in each condition, accounting for 0.69 % in storytelling and 0.52 % in retelling. Finally, in the reintroduction category ($n = 187$ in storytelling and $n = 291$ in retelling), definite noun phrases were the most dominant, occurring 154 times in storytelling (82.35 %) and 245 times in retelling (84.19 %). Pronouns were used to a lesser extent, appearing 10 times in storytelling (5.35 %) and 31 times in retelling (10.65 %). Indefinite noun phrases were also infrequent, with 15 occurrences in storytelling (8.02 %) and 13 in retelling (4.47 %). Bare nouns were the least common, appearing 8 times in storytelling (4.28 %) and only twice in retelling (0.69 %). Notably, several bare nouns were used incorrectly: four instances in the storytelling task and one instance in the retelling task.

To address the third research question, Spearman rank-order correlations were used to analyze the relationships between oral narrative skills and lower-level language skills across both storytelling and retelling tasks. The results are presented in Appendices 1 and 2.

Storytelling. At the macrostructural level, receptive vocabulary was positively correlated with comprehension question performance ($r = 0.531^{**}, p = .006$). No other macro- or microstructural parameters showed significant correlations with lower-level language skills. However, receptive vocabulary and phonological working memory were strongly correlated with each other ($r = 0.780^{**}, p < .001$). Macro- and microstructural parameters were interrelated: story structure correlated with structural complexity ($r = 0.455^{*}, p = .022$), and structural complexity correlated with comprehension questions ($r = 0.536^{**}, p = .006$). Story structure was also positively associated with microstructural measures, including total number of words ($r = 0.536^{**}, p = .006$), total number of different words ($r = 0.606^{**}, p = .001$), and syntactic complexity ($r = 0.461^{*}, p = .020$). Performance on comprehension questions was further associated with the total number of different words ($r = 0.403^{*}, p = .046$). At the microstructural level, the total number of words correlated positively with the total number of different words ($r = 0.944^{**}, p < .001$), number of C-units ($r = 0.571^{**}, p = .003$), and syntactic complexity ($r = 0.504^{*}, p = .010$). Similarly, the total number of different words correlated with the number of C-units ($r = 0.424^{*}, p = .035$) and syntactic complexity ($r = 0.603^{**}, p = .001$). Notably, lexical diversity was negatively correlated with total number of words ($r = -0.782^{**}, p < .001$), total number of different words ($r = -0.500^{*}, p = .011$), and number of C-units ($r = -0.732^{**}, p < .001$).

Retelling. No significant correlations were observed between macro- or microstructural parameters and lower-level language skills. At the macrostructural level, story structure correlated positively with total number of words ($r = 0.587^{**}, p = .002$) and total number of different words ($r = 0.445^{*}, p = .026$), and structural complexity correlated with number of C-units ($r = 0.455^{*}, p = .022$). At the microstructural level, total number of words correlated with total number of different words ($r = 0.831^{**}, p < .001$), and syntactic complexity was positively associated with total number of words ($r = 0.630^{**}, p < .001$) and total number of different words ($r = 0.716^{**}, p < .001$). In contrast, number of C-units was negatively correlated with syntactic complexity ($r = -0.505^{**}, p = .010$).

Table 3

Proportion of definite NPs, indefinite NPs, pronouns and bare nouns in first introduction, maintenance and reintroduction in storytelling.

Variable	First introduction	Maintenance	Reintroduction
Definite NPs	43.94 % (58)	47.92 % (69)	82.35 % (154)
Indefinite NPs	40.91 % (54)	1.39 % (2)	8.02 % (15)
Pronouns	0 % (0)	50.00 % (72)	5.35 % (10)
Bare nouns	15.15 % (20)	0.69 % (1)	4.28 % (8)
Total	100 % (132)	100 % (144)	100 % (187)

Note. Absolute frequencies in brackets.

Table 4

Proportion of definite NPs, indefinite NPs, pronouns and bare nouns in first introduction, maintenance and reintroduction in retelling.

Variable	First introduction	Maintenance	Reintroduction
Definite NPs	36.60 % (56)	23.32 % (45)	84.19 % (245)
Indefinite NPs	54.25 % (83)	1.55 % (3)	4.47 % (13)
Pronouns	0 % (0)	74.61 % (144)	10.65 % (31)
Bare nouns	9.15 % (14)	0.52 % (1)	0.69 % (2)
Total	100 % (153)	100 % (193)	100 % (291)

Note. Absolute frequencies in brackets.

Fig. 1. Proportion of definite NPs, indefinite NPs, pronouns and bare nouns in three referential functions in storytelling.

Fig. 2. Proportion of definite NPs, indefinite NPs, pronouns and bare nouns in three referential functions in retelling.

In summary, the storytelling and retelling tasks exhibited distinct correlation patterns. In storytelling, lower-level language skills (receptive vocabulary and phonological working memory) were associated only with performance on the comprehension questions and not with any other narrative measures. In retelling, by contrast, lower-level language skills did not correlate with any macro- or microstructural parameters. Moreover, a negative correlation between C-units and syntactic complexity emerged in the retelling task but not in storytelling, whereas C-units correlated with structural complexity only in retelling. Overall, storytelling revealed a broader network of relationships across macro- and microstructural levels, while retelling showed a more limited pattern.

4. Discussion

This cross-sectional study is the first to compare the narrative skills of German-speaking children and adolescents with hearing loss in two different narrative tasks - storytelling and retelling - at the macro- and microstructural levels. Additionally, we analyzed the use of referential elements and their application in three distinct referential functions across both narrative tasks. Furthermore, we explored the correlations between narrative skills, receptive vocabulary, and phonological working memory, while also investigating how these relationships differed between the two task types, storytelling and retelling. While extensive research has explored macro- and microstructural skills in storytelling and retelling among monolingual and bilingual children (e.g., Kunnari et al., 2016; Lindgren, 2023; Wehmeier, 2020), as well as those with DLD (e.g., Kuvač Kraljević et al., 2020), and while the use of referential elements and functions has been examined in these groups, much less is known about students with hearing loss.

Narrative task comparison at macro- and microstructural level

The findings of the present study show that students with hearing loss performed better overall in the retelling task. At the macrostructural level, they significantly achieved higher scores in the retellings task. This result is consistent with previous research using the MAIN with monolingual children (Lindgren, 2023; Wehmeier, 2019), monolingual and bilingual children (Kunnari et al., 2016; Otwinowska et al., 2020; Roch et al., 2016; Wehmeier, 2020), as well as children with DLD (Kuvač Kraljević et al., 2020) or those at risk for such disorders (Sheng et al., 2020). These studies demonstrated that children tend to achieve higher scores in the retelling task of the MAIN for story structure compared to the storytelling task. Our study indicates that this pattern can also be found in students with hearing loss. In addition, the results also support existing findings that use other narrative assessment methods and suggest that capturing the macrostructure of a story is generally facilitated when retelling than when generating a story independently in students with hearing loss (Walker et al., 2023) and mono- and bilingual children (Lever & Sénéchal, 2011; Meier & Neitzel, 2023; Schneider & Dubé, 2005). One explanation for these results is that children and adolescents are able to rely on the content and structure provided by the oral model during retelling (Lindgren, 2023; Meier & Neitzel, 2023). This scaffolding effect can facilitate the organization of narrative elements, leading to more complete and complex retellings, also in students with hearing loss. Furthermore, our study revealed that story comprehension was better in the retelling task than in the storytelling task, aligning with prior studies employing the MAIN. Similarly, these studies identified a significant difference between storytelling and retelling in comprehension questions, with scores being significantly higher in the retelling task (Otwinowska et al., 2020; Roch et al., 2016; Wehmeier, 2020). Lindgren (2023) reports that comprehension questions generally exhibit high accuracy, suggesting that children can effectively understand and retain the key elements of a narrative, irrespective of the task type in the MAIN.

Additionally, narratives of the students with hearing loss in the retelling task were significantly longer, exhibited a higher total word count, and contained more utterances. They also displayed greater syntactic complexity, indicating that the oral model not only supports macrostructural organization but also facilitates the implementation of microstructural parameters in students with hearing loss. An exception to this pattern is observed in the analysis of lexical diversity. Lexical diversity was assessed using two parameters: the total number of different words and lexical diversity measured through lemmatization. While the total number of different words was significantly higher in the retelling task, lemmatized lexical diversity was greater in the storytelling task. One possible explanation for this discrepancy is the method of calculating lemmatization, where longer narratives with a higher total word count result in lower lexical diversity. These findings are congruent with prior research indicating that children without hearing loss tend to realize a slightly higher number of different words in retelling tasks (Wofford et al., 2022 for children with developmental language disorder (DLD) and that retellings are linguistically more complex (Duinmeijer et al., 2012, in children with DLD). However, it is important to note that studies involving children with DLD have reported no significant differences between storytelling and retelling in terms of syntactic complexity (Duinmeijer et al., 2012; Otwinowska et al., 2020; Wofford et al., 2022). This may indicate that children with DLD may not derive the same benefit from retelling and that their syntactic difficulties persist regardless of task format, in contrast to students with hearing loss who benefit from the presented model story.

Referential elements and functions in storytelling and retelling

To address the second research question, we examined the use of referential elements and functions in storytelling and retelling. The analysis revealed differences between the two task types. Overall, the students used more referential elements in the retelling task than in the storytelling task. In both conditions, definite noun phrases were the most frequently used category, followed by pronouns and indefinite noun phrases, while bare nouns were the least frequent. Notably, bare nouns appeared even less frequently in retelling than in storytelling. The descriptive results suggest that the narrative model provided in the retelling task encouraged students to incorporate referential elements more frequently to reconstruct the story coherently. Moreover, the students primarily referred to already established entities in both task types and used pragmatically appropriate definite nominal phrases and pronouns to structure their stories effectively.

In both task types, the students predominantly introduced new entities using indefinite noun phrases, followed by definite noun phrases. However, the proportion of first introductions with indefinite and definite noun phrases was higher in the retelling condition. No first introductions using pronouns were observed in either task, indicating that the participants generally adhered to pragmatically appropriate forms for introducing new entities, with slightly higher accuracy in retelling. The high rate of correct introductions is likely due to the relatively advanced age of the students, suggesting that they do not exhibit significant difficulties in this aspect of language use. The finding that children and adolescents more frequently use noun phrases than pronouns to introduce characters is consistent with the study of Lindgren and colleagues (2022), who examined referential elements in first introductions among bilingual children. Furthermore, they reported that as children's age increased, bilingual children showed a preference for using indefinite noun phrases to introduce characters rather than pronouns (Lindgren et al., 2022). In the maintenance category, pronouns were the most frequently used referential element in both tasks, with a significantly higher frequency in the retelling task compared to the storytelling task. In

contrast, definite noun phrases occurred more frequently in storytelling than in retelling. This could indicate that to maintain cohesion students used definite noun phrases to refer to specific entities in both tasks, while they relied more heavily on pronouns in the retelling task. The high frequency of pronouns in the retelling may reflect the need to efficiently refer to already established characters in the narrative. Lindgren and Vogels (2018) observed similar findings regarding reference maintenance in monolingual children, noting that these children primarily used pronouns. Indefinite noun phrases played a minimal role in the maintenance category in both tasks, showing that students are able to use correct grammatical forms to maintain references. Reintroductions accounted for the highest proportion of referential expressions, particularly in the retelling task compared to the storytelling task. Definite noun phrases were the dominant referent element in both conditions, while pronouns and indefinite noun phrases were used less frequently for reintroductions. Pronouns appeared more often in retelling than in storytelling, suggesting that students relied on them for efficient reference tracking in retold narratives. This is consistent with the function of reintroduction, where students typically refer back to previously introduced entities in a precise manner. The predominant use of definite noun phrases for reintroducing characters is consistent with the results of Lindgren and Vogels (2018), who found a similar effect in a storytelling task with monolingual children. Bare nouns were used in all three categories, although not often. The majority of these bare nouns were used adequately, as they represent plural forms that can be used without a determiner. In German, bare nouns can occur after prepositions, particularly in expressions where the noun is often understood in an abstract sense or as an uncountable mass (e.g., food). This indicates that students predominantly used them when referring to general categories rather than specific entities. Regarding the grammatical accuracy of bare nouns, a few errors were observed in both tasks.

Correlations between narrative skills, receptive vocabulary and phonological working memory

The third aim of our study was to investigate relations between narrative skills at the macro- and microstructural level and lower-level language skills in students with hearing loss in both task types. On the macrostructural level, a correlation was observed only between receptive vocabulary and comprehension questions, with no significant associations found with other macro- or microstructural parameters for storytelling. This implies that vocabulary supports the comprehension and recall of narrative elements in the storytelling task but are not directly related to structural aspects like structural complexity or story structure. In contrast, for retelling, no correlations between receptive vocabulary and macrostructure were found. This suggests that, unlike in storytelling, a better vocabulary knowledge may play a less significant role when retelling a story, possibly because the narrative structure is already provided and does not require as much lexical planning. Furthermore, no correlations were found between the two task types, phonological working memory and microstructural skills, indicating that factors such as lexical diversity or syntactic complexity were not significantly influenced by receptive vocabulary and phonological working memory skills in both task types. The results partly contrast with previous research. Hardebeck and colleagues (2024) found a positive correlation between receptive vocabulary and microstructural parameters, such as lexical diversity and syntactic complexity, as well as a negative correlation with the number of C-units in a storytelling task. Moreover, Jones and colleagues (2016) as well as Boons and colleagues (2013) identified a correlation between expressive vocabulary and microstructure in a storytelling and in a retelling task. However, no such correlations were observed in the present study. Additionally, divergent findings were observed regarding the correlations at the macrostructural level. While the present study found correlations between comprehension questions and receptive vocabulary in the storytelling task, Hardebeck and colleagues (2024) identified correlations between story structure, structural complexity, and phonological working memory. Similarly, Jones et al. (2016) found a relationship between expressive vocabulary and macrostructure. One possible explanation for these differences could be that Hardebeck and colleagues (2024) studied a larger sample, which included children without hearing loss, and utilized a different assessment method to measure phonological working memory. Furthermore, Jones and colleagues (2016) employed a different storytelling task, using a video as a narrative stimulus, which may have influenced the observed correlations.

In both tasks, longer narratives—with a higher total number of words and more different word—were positively associated with better story structure, as was greater syntactic complexity in storytelling. Additionally, in the storytelling task, a more diverse vocabulary was associated with better performance on comprehension questions, whereas in retelling, narratives containing more utterances tended to show greater structural complexity. These findings suggest that in storytelling, richer vocabulary use supports story understanding, while in retelling, producing a higher number of utterances contributes to the elaboration and complexity of the narrative. Further analysis revealed positive correlations between the microstructural parameters—total number of words, total number of different words, syntactic complexity and (in storytelling only) number of C-units—in both tasks. This pattern suggests that more linguistically complex narratives, characterized by a diverse vocabulary and more linguistically complex narratives, characterized by a diverse vocabulary and more advanced syntactic structures, are indicative of stronger narrative skills. Additionally, macrostructural elements were positively correlated in the storytelling condition, highlighting a link between better story comprehension and improved story structure and structural complexity. These findings align with Hardebeck and colleagues (2024), who also observed interconnections between macro- and microstructural parameters in storytelling. Moreover, negative correlations in the storytelling condition between lexical diversity and other microstructural parameters, such as total number of words, total number of different words, and C-units, suggest that as the length and complexity of the narrative increase, lexical diversity tends to decrease. A possible explanation for this trend is that as narratives become more extensive, there is a higher likelihood of repetitive words or phrases being used, which limits the overall lexical variation. This finding is consistent with research by Hardebeck et al. (2024), who observed that children with hearing loss used more C-units but demonstrated lower lexical diversity and receptive vocabulary. Additionally, a negative correlation between the number of C-units and syntactic complexity in the retelling condition indicates that narratives with a higher number of utterances tend to exhibit reduced syntactic complexity, possibly because some students are more focused on remembering the content and less on the linguistic realization of the story.

Limitations and future directions

This study is exploratory study in nature, and the sample may not be representative of the broader population of students with hearing loss, particularly due to its limited size and wide age range. Future research with larger samples is needed to confirm and expand upon these results. Furthermore, comparing the narrative skills of students with hearing loss to those of students without hearing loss in both task types, as well examining the use and function of referential elements, could provide valuable insights for clinical and educational practice.

5. Conclusion

This study is the first to investigate the narrative skills of German-speaking students with hearing loss, comparing their performance on storytelling and retelling tasks at both macro- and microstructural levels. The findings indicate that participants performed better on the retelling task, suggesting a scaffolding effect from the oral model provided in this condition. Additionally, differences in the use of referential elements were observed, with participants relying more on noun phrases for first introductions, pronouns for maintenance, and definite noun phrases in retelling.

Correlational analyses revealed an association between narrative skills and receptive vocabulary, specifically with respect to performance on the comprehension questions in the storytelling task. However, no further correlations were found with other macrostructural or microstructural parameters, nor with phonological working memory.

Overall, the findings support previous results that different narrative tasks impose distinct linguistic demands on students with hearing loss. Retelling tasks are particularly effective for assessing narrative skills within extended spontaneous speech samples, offering experimental control over linguistic variables such as length and complexity. In contrast, storytelling tasks, which require independent story construction, may be more diagnostically valuable for evaluating advanced narrators due to their greater complexity and open-ended nature.

Data availability statement

The dataset used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Funding

This work was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy – EXC 2177 /1 – Project ID 390895286, as well as by the Niedersächsisches Ministerium für Wissenschaft und Kultur (MWK, Ministry of Science and Culture) within the funding scheme 'ExzellenzStärken'.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lara Hardebeck: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ulla Licandro:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Paula Bartsch:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Esther Ruigendijk:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all participants and their families as well as all participating schools and teachers.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.jcomdis.2025.106613](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcomdis.2025.106613).

Appendix 1. Correlations between narrative skills and lower-level language skills in storytelling

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1 PPVT	-									
2 Mottier	.780**	-								

(continued on next page)

(continued)

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
3 Story structure	.010	−0.048	-							
4 Structural complexity	.314	.203	.455*	-						
5 Comprehension questions	.531**	.277	.314	.536**	-					
6 TNW	−0.141	.004	.536**	.116	.289	-				
7 TNDW	−0.062	.035	.606**	.229	.403*	.944*	-			
8 Lexical diversity	.238	.113	−0.157	.196	.063	−0.782**	−0.500*	-		
9 Number of C-units	−0.125	.087	.174	.092	.113	.571**	.424*	−0.732**	-	
10 Syntactic complexity	−0.140	−0.243	.461*	.041	.190	.504*	.603**	−0.086	−0.368	-

Note. PPVT-4 = T-score of the Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test (Lenhard et al., 2015); Mottier = T-score of the Mottier-Test according to Wild and Fleck (2013); TNW = total number of words; TNDW = total number of different words; Spearman rank-order correlation. * indicates $p < .05$. ** indicates $p < 0,01$.

Appendix 2. Correlations between narrative skills and lower-level language skills in retelling

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1 PPVT	-									
2 Mottier	.780**	-								
3 Story structure	.208	.320	-							
4 Structural complexity	−0.055	.058	.278	-						
5 Comprehension questions	.198	.007	−0.007	−0.065	-					
6 TNW	.293	.177	.587**	.019	.157	-				
7 TNDW	.351	.106	.445*	−0.067	.219	.831**	-			
8 Lexical diversity	.166	.080	−0.289	−0.037	.063	−0.341	.116	-		
9 Number of C-units	.315	.314	.332	.455*	−0.069	.167	−0.062	−0.307	-	
10 Syntactic complexity	.043	−0.174	.156	−0.294	.275	.630**	.716**	−0.070	−0.505**	-

Note. PPVT-4 = T-score of the Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test (Lenhard et al., 2015); Mottier = T-score of the Mottier-Test according to Wild and Fleck (2013); TNW = total number of words; TNDW = total number of different words; Spearman rank-order correlation. * indicates $p < .05$. ** indicates $p < 0,01$.

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